

MOTIVATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF FAIRY TALES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK FOLKLORE

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Annotation

The present article studies the motivational features of English and Uzbek tales and their importance in folklore. This research considers the field of folklore as the main subject of its study. The aim of the work is to develop the studying fairy tales and make contributions to the fields of linguistics. Besides, in this article the origin of English and Uzbek tales and their types are widely explained.

Key words

fairy tales, linguistics, folklore, motivational features, classification, literature.

INTRODUCTION

The fact that the fairy tale genre was created by the collective simple mind as an attempt to explain incomprehensible things and events to people. A fairy tale is a short story that belongs to the folklore genres.¹ It is pure fiction, people never believed in the truth of what happened in it, its genre task is to entertain the audience. Fairy tales are one of the oldest and most widespread genres and have a high position in world folklore. The studying of fairy tales in different nations has a long history and has been playing an important role in folklore for several decades. It should be noted that tales reflects the mythological ideas, ancient traditions, different beliefs, customs and are full of interesting and extraordinary events. In addition to this, due to the growing interest in fairy tales on a global scale, many linguists are doing scientific work on this genre.

Fairy tales as a genre have undergone a long process of formation. They were created on the basis of primitive people's simple narrating of an event in their life. Storytelling has improved over time.² Needless to say, it is easy to learn and

¹ Jorgonse, Jeana (2022). Fairy tales 101: An Accessible Introduction to Fairy Tales. Fox Folk Press. 372 pages.

² O.Safarov. "O'ZBEK XALQ OG'ZAKI IJODI" «Musiqa» nashriyoti Toshkent 2010. S-201.

understand everything we need through myths, legends and fairy tales. They have a great influence on the human mind, they can amaze and make people want to travel to the past or to the time described in the fairy tale. In addition, through their influence, interest in mythical characters, their place and time increases, and as a result, our interest in the fantastic world increases even more. With the help of fairy tales, it is much easier for us to understand the difference between good and evil, justice and injustice, crookedness and straightness and many other concepts. Consequently, the way of thinking of a person who reads or listens to tales changes and gets motivation. The study of folklore focuses on a wide range of social expression, studies the forms and ways of living that shape the reality of people in society. Children can learn from the mistakes of the characters in these stories, which helps them develop broad, critical thinking skills. Stories are also model behavior for children and provide a context in which children can evaluate their own feelings and decision-making. By listening to fairy tales, children learn the qualities of goodness and differentiate between good and bad and try to be like positive characters.

"A fairy tale for children has its own charm, some secrets of the ancient worldview are revealed. They find in the narrative of a fairy tale, spontaneously, without explanation, something very valuable for them, necessary for the growth of their consciousness".³

Telling stories is a common pastime in the country and is loved by both children and adults. Usually, the storyteller, while talking about the story and characters, reacted live to the audience's reaction and immediately made some corrections to his story. Therefore, fairy tales have become one of the most polished folklore genres. They also best meet the needs of children, organically matching the psychology of children. The pursuit of goodness and justice, belief in miracles, inclination to fantasy, magical transformation of the surrounding world - all this will happily welcome the child in a fairy tale. It should be noted that, truth and goodness always win in fairy tales. No matter what the story tells, it is always on the side of the offended and the victimized. At the same time, it clearly shows where a person's life path leads, what his happiness and unhappiness consist of, and how he differs from animals and birds. Each step of the hero leads him to the goal, to the final success. You have to pay for mistakes, and after you pay, the hero will get lucky again. In such a fantastic movement of fiction, an important feature

³ Бену Анна Борисовна"Символизм сказок и мифов народов мира. Человек - это миф, сказка - это ты" 2011.

of people's perception of the world is expressed - a firm belief in justice, that a noble human principle will inevitably defeat everything that opposes it.

Folklorists have classified fairy tales in various ways. The Aarne-Thompson-Uther classification system and the morphological analysis of Vladimir Propp are among the most notable. Other folklorists have interpreted the tales' significance, but no school has been definitively established for the meaning of the tales. Folktales are classified according to the type of reality they represent, their ideological content, the interpretation of images, artistic language and style, the way they reflect reality, the construction of the plot and composition, and the role and function of imaginary and real fiction. According to these characteristics, folklorist V. Ya. Propp divided Russian folk tales into five types: magical, novelistic, cumulative, about animals and life,⁴ while Uzbek fairy tale scholar M. Afzalov divided fairy tales into fantastic and realistic types, although he adds it to the composition of fantastic tales, he does not adhere to this classification and studies the tales about animals separately, and thus recognizes that Uzbek folk tales have three internal types: a) tales about animals; b) magic-fantasy tales and c) life-satirical tales. His student K.Imomov, based on his teacher's classification, divides Uzbek folk tales into two types, magical and life, and recommends studying animal tales in a series of magical tales.

Besides, the researches of S. Jumaeva and Z. Usmonova clearly confirm that animal tales form a separate group in the series of Uzbek folk tales, as well as novelistic tales. Based on these considerations, it was decided to distinguish three internal types of Uzbek fairy tales. These are the bottom ones:

1. Magic-fantasy tales.
2. Tales about animals.
3. Household-life tales.⁵

CONCLUSION

All in all, the fairy tale does not leave the child as an indifferent observer, but makes him an active participant of the events, he experiences every failure and every victory together with the heroes. The fairy tale teaches him to think that evil must be punished in any case. The fairy tale, which is one of the most developed genres of folklore and children's favorite, reflects the world with all its integrity, complexity and beauty more clearly and brightly than other types of art. The study of folklore focuses on examining the forms and ways of living through which communities shape their reality. Children have chances to learn from the mistakes

⁴ Propp V. Morphology of a fairy tale. – —Azбука-Atticus, 1986.

⁵ O.Safarov. "O'ZBEK XALQ OG'ZAKI IJODI" «Musiqqa» nashriyoti Toshkent 2010. S-208.

of characters in these stories, which help them with their critical thinking skills. Furthermore, fairy tales are also model behavior for children and provide a context in which children can easily evaluate their own emotions and decision making.

REFERENCES:

1. Jorgonse, Jeana (2022). *Fairy tales 101: An Accessible Introduction to Fairy Tales*. Fox Folk Press. 372 pages.
2. O.Safarov. "O'ZBEK XALQ OG'ZAKI IJODI" «Musiq» nashriyoti Toshkent 2010. S-201.
3. Бену Анна Борисовна"Символизм сказок и мифов народов мира. Человек - это миф, сказка - это ты" 2011.
4. Propp V. *Morphology of a fairy tale*. —Azbuka-Atticus, 1986. — p.11.
5. Sulzberger, Mayer (1917), "Joseph Jacobs", *The American Jewish Year Book*, 18: p 69.
6. Sarvinoz, A., & Maftuna, A. (2023). LINGUOCULTURAL PECULARITIES OF THE UZBEK GEORTONYM NAVRUZ. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 3(28), 180-186.
7. Alimov, S. S., & Yusupova, O. M. (2022). LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF BORROWINGS FROM ENGLISH TO UZBEK LANGUAGE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(1), 1-4.
8. Hakimova, Z. T. (2021). The analysis of metaphors and metonymies in political speeches. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 10(12), 721-726
9. Ravshanjonovna, K. S. (2023). The Meaning of Causative Verbs. *Jurnal Multidisiplin Madani*, 3(1), 14-18.
10. Parpieva Mokhirakhon, Inomova Xurmatoy, & Muqaddam Jurayeva. (2023). A METHOD OF SOUND ORGANIZATION OF ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN ARTISTIC TEXT USING PHONOTYLISTIC LANGUAGE. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 2(4), 135-139
11. XOLIQOVA Zulxumor, & XOLDOROVA Hilola. (2023). FEATURES OF W. SHAKESPEARE'S WORKS MORPHOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES. *ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ*, 3(3), 17-20.
12. Tojiboyeva M., Pakirdinova S. OLAMNING LISONIY MANZARASIDA DONOLIK VA NODONLIK KONSEPTLARI // *Involta Scientific Journal*. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 154-158.

13. Mamadjanova, M. U. (2022). O 'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA EPITETNING CHOQ 'ISHTIRMA TADQIQI. ANTONAMAZIYA EPITETLAR. RESEARCH AND EDUCATION, 1(5), 110-115

14. QADIMGI SHUMER, RIM VA YUNONLARNING O'LCHOV TIZIMLARI S Adxamova. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences 2 (12), 43-47 2023.